

A Study of Indigenous Tribes Tourism Developing-Case by Lilang, Tbulan, and Hrung in Taiwan

Chu-Chu Liao, Ying-Xing Lin

Abstract—The purpose of the study is to analyze the main tourism attraction in indigenous tribes, as well as for the development of tribal aboriginal tourism brings positive and negative impacts. This study used qualitative research methods, and Lilang, Tbulan, and Hrung three tribes as the object of investigation. The results showed that: 1. Because three tribes geographical proximity, but have their own development characteristics, not conflict situations. 2. Three tribes are located in National Scenic Area and National Forest Recreation Area near, so driven tribal tourism development. 3 In addition Hrung three tribal no major attraction, mainly located in the provision of accommodation; another Lilang and Tbulan tribe has natural resources and cultural resources attraction. 4 in the tourism brings positive and negative impacts, respondents expressed positive than residents of negative impacts. Based on the above findings, this study not only provides advice for tribal tourism operators, but also for future research to provide specific directions.

Keywords—Indigenous tourism, tribes tourism, tourism developing, impact, attraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

SINCE the United Nations in 1993 designated as the "International year for Indigenous People", the global rise of an "isolated", "novelty", "strange customs" in indigenous areas in the tourism potential of tidal activity. At present, Taiwan's indigenous groups recognized by the government are divided into fourteen families, ethnic groups according to their geographical location, customs and develop different tribal cultures. Coupled with the Taiwan government for indigenous cultural preservation of great importance to the development of an indigenous ceremony packages include tourism itineraries, promote indigenous industrial projects and so on. Therefore follow this wave of indigenous tourism boom, regional or visit aboriginal tribes of Taiwan's emerging tourist trip a major feature [1]. While the depth of indigenous tourism in Taiwan is an important tourist attraction, but the development so far, but there have been many difficulties, for example, some tribes oppose the development of tourism; tourism development that some tribes are inadequate conditions, resulting in the development of tourism service quality is poor emergence situation. Purpose of this study is to analyze the main tourist attractive force indigenous tribes, and to analyze the

development of tourism for indigenous tribes brought positive and negative impact, hoping to provide other indigenous tribes in the development of a reference for tourism.

II. THEORY FOUNDATION

A. Indigenous Tourism

Indigenous tourism is a kind of resource-based tourism type, and indigenous culture as a major tourist attraction [2], the development of tourism in addition to the local beautiful natural landscapes and exotic alien landscape, the more tourists the "Man" as a very important purpose [3]. Many scholars have defined for aboriginal tourism different definitions, the following illustration:

Ryan and Huyton [4] defines "the aboriginal tourism" is a tourist artistic performances by aboriginal culture, celebrations, attractions, historical heritage and customs attract while traveling to tourist activities engaged in aboriginal areas.

Wu [5] believes that "Aboriginal tourism" is different from the general patterns of tourism activities, because the contacts are not stiff rides or unable to talk with natural resources, but people who live, authentic cultural traditions. And "Aboriginal tourism" is defined as: the development of Aboriginal cultural resources as a spindle, the evolved Things; activities connotations include: Aboriginal arts and crafts, clothing, architecture, music, dance, cultural traditions, etc.

Chang [6] in cola tribal study, "Aboriginal tourism" is defined as: "Aboriginal tribes use their own national culture surrounding ecological environment and resources as tourism and recreation, tourist pilgrimage through the tribal culture, visiting heritage, dance performances, life experience, guided tours and other business marketing methods to observe and learn about Aboriginal culture traits of activities."

Chang [7] pointed out that the Aboriginal tourism within the area defined as the aboriginal tribes, enjoy and experience the unique culture of indigenous peoples and natural ecological resources, and the creation of local Aboriginal welfare of the subject of one kind of the ultimate purpose of things.

Lin [8] study Taitung Amis *Erythrina fall* tourism development, it is considered whether by anthropologists considered "alien tourism" the meaning of the cross-cultural experience and contacts activities; or most scholars place in indigenous areas of concern various tourist phenomena, and even caused a discussion on various topics, broadly can be called "Aboriginal tourism" the scope of the discussion. The form and type of its development, it may be due to the social

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culture of various ethnic groups, and natural resources and all differences; each aboriginal tribe may at their discretion special social and cultural, and tourism resources of different subjective intention, plan out different activities connotations. Therefore Jufan to "Aboriginal culture" as the core resources and characteristics of the various types of tourism activities can call "aboriginal tourism."

B. Attraction

Lin [9] study of consciousness Thao aboriginal tourism attraction, and found that the sense of aboriginal resources are attractive to tourists, including the "quiet enjoyment", "get relaxed pleasure", "family ties" can be seen as a major tourist recreation motivation, and "the pursuit of peace of mind" as agreed with the highest level of tourist character.

Huang and Luo [10] study public participation in Wutai Township, Pingtung County aboriginal ecotourism behavioral intention, attitude, belief in dimensions, the results showed that people think your choice of Wutai Township for eco-tourism, can improve understanding of aboriginal culture cognition and experience, enhance the natural ecology of knowledge and experience, to relieve physical and mental stress, physical exercise, satisfy curiosity, in line with tourism trends, promote parent-child relationships, enhance social relationships, enhance their environmental awareness and promote active participation in the environment has been conservation movement, increase their respect for indigenous culture and identity, as well as to promote active participation from Aboriginal culture preservation.

C. Tourism Impacts

Indigenous tribes in the relevant research, Wu [11] study Alishan Township, Chiayi County village's residents over the age of 18, the sample selection to all households in the village as a unit, to conduct a survey of household's access, a total of 145 valid sample. The results showed: Residents background characteristics, although occupation, educational attainment, personal income and family life cycle all in one, two perceptual reach significant differences, but live number of years but it is affecting tourism impact awareness of the most significant variables. In addition, the degree of community attachment, tourism planning and tourism degree of participation interests with the residents also depend on the extent of the impact of the perception of a significant correlation.

Huang and Luo [10] study public participation in Wutai Township, Pingtung County aboriginal ecotourism behavioral intention, attitude, belief in dimensions, the results showed that people think your choice of Wutai Township for eco-tourism can promote local economic development, create Aboriginal employment opportunities, enhance local government tax revenue, improve Aboriginal self-identity, enhance and improve the local image in the region and enhance the preservation of aboriginal culture and heritage, enhance the local natural ecological resources to protect, promote ethnic harmony and so on.

Chen [12] studied the impact of Lishan Aborigines and development strategy for tourism and found that Aboriginal

economic, social, cultural, and ecological aspects of environmental impact, positive impact were: to increase employment, income, labor force, history and culture promotion, and infrastructure improvements; in negative shocks, including security problems, promote industrial development of foreign tourists picking product behavior, as well as foreign investment in the industrial structure of foreign influence.

Chen [13] studied the development of the local residents Smangus tribe B industry impact, and found 82% of respondents tribal population, for the "implementation of the number of regulatory holidays", "combining eco-tourism" and "combining traditional culture" to develop B & B Industry, which means that a high degree of support. Another 18% of the respondents that had no comments or objections hold negative attitudes. For B & B industry tribal peoples cognitive shocks to "joint operations" successfully resolved the conflict between tribal people. For the "Future Development guesthouse owners' attitude part, 50% of the respondents had no comments, 16% of the respondents are opposed to a negative attitude, and another 34% of the respondents had no comments. For the "B & B industry impact cognition", the whole, the local B & B industry brought about the economic, social and cultural impact, positive than negative. In the "physical environment" impact is also negative than positive.

Chen and Kuo [14] study Wutai Township, Pingtung County tourism impact Aboriginal feelings, and found that respondents generally feel more for the tourism impact of the hold positive attitude, and that the development of tourism can "enhance the local visibility", "improving public facilities", "help community residents to interact more closely", and "to increase employment opportunities for residents". But residents also think that the development will have a negative impact on tourism, including: "visiting friends and relatives to increase the number of financial burden" and "causing local price increases."

Lee and Hung [15] studied Sandiman villages Paiwan tribe indigenous cultural tourism industry, the results showed that: 1. Tourism development for the tribe types of economic benefits arising from increased local employment opportunities, thus making the local culture has been extended; 2. village tribesmen have three quality criteria to aboriginal craft products such as clay, wood carving, stone carving, tapestries, clothing, glass beads, weaving, bronze knives, etc., in order to enrich the tribe cultural pride but also has a deep sense of identity; 3. tourism development resulting from external conflict: the manufacture of tourists in tribal mess and noise, to have a bad impression tribesmen; while the internal conflict in the tourism business and the competitive impact interpersonal tribal tribe mutual cultural identity; 4 three tribal tribe village's traditional culture also has an innovative approach; "willing to share" traditional values may gradually fade away.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Overview of the Study Area

Heping District, located in the northeast corner of Taichung City, covers an extensive area of 1037.8 square kilometers of peace, is the city's most twenty-nine vast area of the first region, a total of equality, the Lishan, the fraternity, the sheave, the situation in the South, in the pit, freedom, the concept of waiting for up to eight years. East Forest Hills Central Mountain Lake, north of Snow Mountains, south of Acacia Hill, Dayuling surrounded by mountains and across the valley from Tachia River them into complete natural boundaries. Special geographical conditions in this area, north of the Snow Mountains, south of Acacia Hill, Yu Ling, mountains retaining ring Tachia River valley, mountains, forests throughout, the unique charm of the magnificent mountains and landscape in Taiwan, more famous, known as Oriental Switzerland reputation. Therefore, the abundant tourism resources and the fruits and vegetables rich in alpine farm in this area have become the two most important economic lifelines. Heping District, famous tourist attractions are: Guguan spa area, Lishan, Wuling Farm, Fushoushan Farm, Heavenly Lake, Snowy Mountains, Baxianshan Forest Recreation Area, the highway landscape, but there are regional specialties: Sweet persimmon, pear, apple, peach, pear mountain cabbage,

cabbage, bamboo shoots etc, mountain vegetables such as fresh sweet [16].

B. Tribes Status

For this study, the statuses of the three tribes are set as described below [17].

1. Lilang Tribe

TABLE I
 INTRODUCE OF LILANG TRIBE STATUS

Tribe characteristics	Lilang by Atayal Language of homophonic Chinese is meaning people coming from the mountains.
Location	Fraternity Village, Heping District, Taichung City
Range	Dajia River is located on the left bank, at the juncture of its tributaries Lilang River southwest mesa.
Geographic environment	Tableland
Race	Atayal
Language	Atayal Language, Pekingese
Religious belief	True Jesus Church, Atayal traditional belief
Tribe Origin	Tribe ancestors came from Nantou County Lixing Village Red cedar tribe, about 1907 first tribe to move to the other side of this Riyan tribe of Bubuear River upstream, five years later, because the Japanese police forces advancing from Dajia River peace and love to Taichung two rural junction of the ridge, which is meager mountain area, the whole tribe of exposure to the Japanese police surveillance range, only in the Japanese police inducement, the turn Biku Mountains, in the clan have been living in the same community long good habitat downstream Dajia River and Lilang River confluence, the establishment of a new tribe so far.
Agricultural products	Peach, Plum, and Mandarin orange

2. Tbulan Tribe

TABLE II
 INTRODUCE OF TBULAN TRIBE STATUS

Tribe characteristics	When the Japanese occupied Taiwan, the tribe known as the "long good habitat" agency, transliterated as "Nikolaos."
Location	Fraternity Village, Heping District, Taichung City
Range	Eighth in Taiwan Highway (east-west highway), facing the Dajia River left bank of the plains, east facing Hrungr tribe, west pick Lilang tribe.
Geographic environment	Level the land
Race	Atayal
Language	Atayal Language, Pekingese
Religious belief	Catholicism, Atayal traditional belief
Tribe Origin	De Fulan tribe sources and also in the cold, like living in Nantou County, led by the leader of this tribe first move to the Eight Immortals, in the Republic three years and then moved to this when Stork present site. Japanese occupation era, De Fulan tribe known as the "long good habitat" agency, transliterated as "Nikolaos", said leader is named after mountains. Chieftain called Kurasu. Kurasu Japanese transliteration character is good habitat for a long time. Until in 50 years time, a mayor realizing the place abounds with pine trees, and often crane their habitat, then went ahead renamed "Stork."
Agricultural products	Mandarin orange, Pear, and , Taiwan Short-leaf Pine

3. Hrung Tribe

TABLE III
INTRODUCE OF TBULAN TRIBE STATUS

Tribe characteristics	Near Guguan Scenic and Baxianshan National Forest Recreation Area
Location	Fraternity Village, Heping District, Taichung City
Range	Located in the highway Shwin Creek about three or four hundred meters above the top platform, Guguan west Tachiachi River right bank.
Geographic environment	Tableland
Race	Atayal
Language	Atayal Language, Pekingese
Religious belief	True Jesus Church, Atayal traditional belief
Tribe Origin	Hrung Taiwan tribesmen originally lived in Nantou County, former Republican leader, led the tribe migrated to Tachiachi basin, was built in a community. In nine Japanese response Beishih group activities tribe chieftain rate hit Shwin Creek and Lilang Creek in Laos brain, killing brain small town of Granville moment, but exhaustion, or surrender, is forced Stork placed in this tribe. In the Republic for 30 years, moved to this Hrung Taiwan regions.
Agricultural products	Peach, persimmon, cabbage

C. Data Collection

In this study, qualitative approach to data collection, the first phase of literature analysis, mainly in the tribal and network related research literature relating to the introduction of three tribes. The second stage is to field studies, study visits by the three tribes, to understand the current situation as well as tribal tourism development situation. The third stage is the interview; the main subjects interviewed were tourists, Tribal Development Association staff, tribal people and tribal tourism and leisure operators (B & B, leisure farms, and food and beverage industry). In order to understand the content of interviews tribal tourist attraction, as well as tourism development to tribal residents feel positive and negative impact of the situation.

D. Data Analysis

Interview data in this study, the analysis of the following main steps: (1) One would interview the information converted into transcripts. (2) The purpose of this study based on the transcripts and interviews about the inner structure of the sentence to be coded. (3) Summarizing transcripts within the meaning of the sentence structure, to be analyzed and discussed. (4) Interviews in this study to increase the reliability and validity of degrees, in the data analysis, the study have invited a professor of tourism and leisure joint discussion and analysis, in order to increase the accuracy of data analysis.

IV. RESULTS

A. Tribes Attraction Analysis

Lilang, Tbulan, and Hrung three tribes located at Scenic Area of Guguan, near a Baxianshan National Forest Recreation Area. Scenic Area of Guguan adjacent to Tachiachi off, because spa fame from scenic spots, where the spa is part of the assessed fine carbonated spring water, the water quality is excellent. Shenmu Valley Vacation Hotel has a thousand five pine sacred trees, the valley off special landscape. Elevation of 2400 meters Baxianshan National Forest Recreation Area, there was one of the former Taiwan's three major forests, and some reputation as one of the eight wonders of Taiwan. Baxianshan surrounded by mountains, lush forests, in addition to rare birds, butterflies perched outside, there is also the two famous springs

in Taiwan "Shwin Greek " and "Jiabao Greek" converge here, seen at the end of its clear streams, water glycol .

After site visits researchers surveyed three tribes, and each tribe to meet by chance the way, asking tourists to assess three major local attraction and tribal tourism service situation, the researchers summarized the main findings in the following table shows.

1. Lilang Tribe

TABLE IV
LILANG TRIBE ATTRACTION AND TOURISM SERVICES

Tribes	Attraction	Tourism Services
	☐ Seventh Heaven Falls ☐ Five Brave Pine Forest Trail ☐ Lilang Forest Trail ☐ Lilang Greek ☐ Tang Madan Mountain ☐ Bai Mo Mountain	☒ Accommodation ☐ Lilenci exploration center B & B ☐ Papa Bear camping area ☐ Tanino Hall ☐ Markuo Legend B & B, camping area ☒ Restaurant ☐ Lilenci exploration center ☐ Tanino Hall ☐ Markuo Legend B & B ☒ Leisure and Recreation ☐ Physical training field (high altitude and low altitude), paintball, cold springs, camping, and the original forest trail. ☐ Hot & cold spring ☐ Mountain hiking
Lilang		

Lilang region late development, still retains the original natural ecology, forest, flora and fauna are very rich, you can see two pine, five pine, incense Nan, Yanan, mountain ephedrine and other native plants, insects, birds, frogs, butterflies and other more are too numerous to mention, is that many ecological observation, photographer's paradise. Lilang Creek steady flow of water throughout the year, and part of the creek bank and the road approaching, attracting many tourists visit daily summer swimming.

2. Tbulan Tribe

TABLE V

TBULAN TRIBE ATTRACTION AND TOURISM SERVICES

Tribes	Attraction	Tourism Services
Tbulan	☐ Baxianshan Forest Trial	■ Accommodation
	☐ Firefly Forest Trial	☐ Millet Spike B & B
	☐ Lanro Temple	☐ Rain Dew of Private House
	☐ Aboriginal traditional architecture	☐ Old Capital Wood B & B
	☐ Japanese traditional architecture	☐ Shennongku Leisure Farm B& B
		■ Restaurant
		☐ Hometown Fish Restaurant
		☐ Rain Dew of Private House
		☐ New Zealand Pasture
		☐ Fairmont Trout Restaurant
		☐ Xianggu Mushroom Pasture
		☐ Shennongku Leisure Farm
		☐ Crane Chi Garden Restaurant
		☐ Kulas Aatyal Style Restaurant
		■ Leisure and Recreation
		☐ Hot & cold spring
		☐ Canyoning
	☐ Mountain hiking	

Tbulan tribes among Tachiachi river coastal three tribes, in the attraction and tourism services, are the most perfect tribe. 921 1999, mainly due to a major earthquake hit central Taiwan in Taichung Tbulan tribe zone of peace cannot be spared, but the 921 earthquake, the tribe as the redevelopment attracts many tourists visit results in 2001 and, 2002 years tourism recovery only but nothing lasts forever, this beautiful tribe, successive floods aftermath of 72, 824 floods, so that all reconstruction achievements burned, leaving the public impression that the television coverage of the affected screen. But these bad scenes stork defeated tribes, quiet decade started again, open in the tribal handicrafts teaching, continue to promote the original features, combined with the original guesthouse owners and host family, planning a series of food and play, cultural characteristics of ecotourism.

3. Hrung Tribe

TABLE VI

HRUNG TRIBE ATTRACTION AND TOURISM SERVICES

Tribes	Attraction	Tourism Services
Hrung	Non	■ Accommodation
		☐ Osai B & B
		☐ Iwangili B & B
		☐ Suyangwanlon B & B
		☐ Datisuyang B & B
		☐ Ganonshocho B & B
		■ Restaurant
		☐ In-In Restaurant
		■ Leisure and Recreation
		☐ Mountain hiking

As Hrung tribe located Guguan Recreation Area and Baxianshan National Forest Recreation Area entrance itself does not attraction, behind in the tribal forest hiking trails for tourists.

Impact Analysis

After in-depth interviews, this studies all the tribes of the positive and negative tourism impacts, as described in the following.

1. Lilang Tribe

Interviews found that respondents Tribe Development Association staff, tribal people and tribal tourism and leisure operators, both reactions because there are tourists tribes, some tribes resident of leisure farms, restaurants, and B & B, so it promotes employment opportunities. But here is not the summer tourist season, but in the winter, because tribal recreation area near Guguan, while the valley off the main attraction is the hot springs. But throughout the year, tourists come to mountain tribe's lot, so when the tourist season, holidays, or there will be tourist's tribes. In the tourism impact, since the Tribe Development Association integration, coupled with government subsidies to create a community as a whole, not only the improvement of public facilities for the entire tribal environment is also very clean, so tribal tourism development, residents generally considered to be positive than negative. Although at any one time in addition to the tourists visiting tribes, especially when the season more tourists, but does not give the tribes on the negative impact to the environment, because the limited capacity of the tribe. Besides the crowds of tourists and more help tribal cultural goods sold, as well as tourists enjoy tribal stay down dining.

2. Tbulan Tribe

In Tbulan tribe, the interviews found that, due Tbulan tribe are severely affected tribes, so visibility tribe known in Taiwan as typhoon and rainstorm, the stations of the tribe are the must-visit places. Also due to hit, so the tribes receive government subsidies to the more, and have a professional team stationed in counseling, so that the various tribal public works perfect, but also in tourism services will be even more perfect. Although Lilang similar tourist season is mainly concentrated in the winter, because of the season came Guguan Recreation Area bathing tourists more, will also take the opportunity to visit the tribe. As tourists came to visit the tribe, tribal marketing of agricultural products to help, along with some tribal inhabitants transformed into tourist services, also increased employment opportunities for tribal people. Overall, the tribal inhabitants of the positive impact that tourism is greater than the negative, plus tribe has planned parking space, thus brought into the tribe due to traffic noise and pollution and not so obvious. The most important is because Every time a typhoon hit, but also the integration of tribal peoples to live together beliefs, sustainable business for the tribe, residents generally support the development of tourism and hospitality come tribal tourists.

3. Hrung Tribe

As Hrung tribe is small and there is no attraction, sightseeing service only offers B & B accommodation, and only five, so there is no obvious positive and negative impact of tourism there. However, because the development of tourism's sake, the tribe's overall public facilities and the environment, the government of subsidies, there are obvious improvements.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusion

According to this study the motivation and purpose, the empirical research, this study has the following conclusions.

- a. In the attraction areas, Lilang, Tbulan and Hrung tribe to attract tourists to the main reasons is the three tribes are located in Lishan National Scenic Area (Guguan Recreation Area) and the National Forest Recreation Area near Baxianshan therefore led to tribal tourism development.
- b. Since the three tribes geographical proximity, but have their own development characteristics, Lilang tribe in tourism development is positioned in the "garden tribe", Tbulan tribe is positioned in the "gourmet tribes" and Hrung tribe is positioned in the "B & B tribe" Although the three tribes proximity, but have their own development characteristics.
- c. In this study, three tribes, in addition to Hrung tribe no major attraction, mainly located in the provision of accommodation, so in tribal development, is not dominated by tourism development, because most of the residents still dominated by farming, coupled with tribes on the scale is not big. Also Lilang and Tbulan tribe has natural resources and cultural resources attraction, is to attract tourists to visit the main tribe. On the tourism services, the Tbulan tribe is significantly better than the other two tribes. But Lilang tribe late development, and therefore still retains many of the original forest scenery and trails, plus the leisure farm offers adventure facilities, but also to attract visitors to the tribe of the main factors.
- d. In the tourism develop brings positive and negative impacts, respondents expressed positive than residents of negative impacts. Then three tribes, such as the actual situation in terms of, Hrung tribe and no obvious feelings tourism brings positive or negative impacts. And Lilang and Tbulan tribes because tribes are obviously feeling the positive impact tourism development impact is greater than the negative impact, but because of tribal tourism development reasons, the sale of agricultural products to help local residents employment opportunities, as well as increased tribal economic income.
- e. Residents interviewed various tribes' reaction that Taiwan Provincial Highway No. VIII still belong to interrupt, Guguan various tribes and Lishan link need to bypass Nantou to arrive, so the whole journey takes four hours to reach (was originally a one hour), resulting in the development of tourism throughout the region blocked. Because of the above reasons, why only in winter, when the Guguan is considered relevant areas season. Roads were not interrupted before the tourist's all the year round visiting tribes, but now it is time to go to the tourist season, have a large number of tourists come, which is currently on a three tribal main obstacle to tourism development.

B. Suggestions

According to the analysis of the results of this study suggest the following:

- a. Current the VIII of Taiwan Provincial Highway still belong interruption, although Taiwan Power Company's Castle sidewalk open to Lishan local residents and Guguan access, but is only open three times a day, and not open to tourists, and the whole tourism development moving lines blocked. Suggested government units to deal with the local into the environment assessment, identify areas does not affect the local ecology, alternative road for the construction of 921 before the earthquake to restore relations with the Lishan region's prosperity.
- b. In this study, although the specific interviews with local tribal residents and tourism operators, while also interviews with tourists, but visitors are not many aspects of the interview data. Therefore, for subsequent studies, suggest researchers may interview in the local tourist accommodation and mountain climbing, specifically about their satisfaction with the services for tribal tourism situation.

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